

Research programme to share knowledge and improve uptake of new digital technologies in sheep and goat farming

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RESEARCH NEEDS AND GAPS IN SOLUTIONS

Sm@RT POLICY BRIEFS

Sm@ll Ruminant Technologies

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Introduction

General introduction about the project

Sm@RT (Small Ruminant technologies –Precision Livestock Farming & Digital technologies for small ruminants) is a European network to share experience of new technologies for sheep and goats. It brings together a network of researchers, farmers and advisors to improve awareness of innovative tools, demonstrating their potential and possible return on investment.

Sm@RT involved 11 partners in 8 countries, and focus on dairy goats, dairy sheep and meat sheep farmers.

Sm@RT fostered exchanges on technologies between farmers during farm demonstration days on innovative farms and digifarms.

Sm@RT created resources for farmers regarding available technologies, to progress in their digitization process to meet their needs and objectives. Guidelines, cost-benefit analysis, farmers' testimonies and videos have been created to encourage uptake of solutions to needs.

Findings

In general, the findings of this project confirm that:

- 🐄 Although only 15 % of farmers have technologies on their farms, 79% of them would like to use technologies to help with feeding/grazing, health and welfare, reproduction, flock/herd management, fattening and/or milking
- 🐄 A total of 166 ranked needs were identified and 60 innovative technology solutions were proposed to the farmers.
- 🐄 Training sessions on Digifarms and Farm Demonstration on Innovative farms proved an ideal medium for peer-to-peer knowledge transfer regarding the use of technologies.
- 🐄 The main barriers to uptake are linked to costs of technologies, but also to the lack of training options, after-sales advice, confidence in one's skills and compatibility between the devices.
- 🐄 Sharing of knowledge and experiences between farmers, researchers and other stakeholders in different countries proved invaluable.
- 🐄 There is a lot of information regarding cost of technologies, but the information is often dispersed and not always in a format (or language) easy to understand or to adapt to one's farming situation. Cost-benefit analyses are necessary for farmers to fully decide on investing in technologies or not.

The project identified 4 key messages, that are developed in policy briefs:

1. Focus on research needs
2. Peer-to-peer demonstration & training needs for farmers
3. Innovations on small ruminant farms
4. Adoption & uptake of innovative technologies

This policy brief focus on key message #1 – Focus on research needs

*The recommendations identified in the four policy briefs have been developed during the life of the project by the partners and in collaboration with **over 1350** stakeholders during the project's participatory workshops.*

*The project carried out an initial online survey to capture farmers' opinions, which gathered **over 660** answers. A total of **52** national workshops have been conducted, together with **five** transnational workshops, **one** final seminar and **one** international visit. **Over 635** individual farmers' evaluations have collected during **30** training sessions and farm demonstrations days on Digifarms and Innovative Farms.*

Recommendation at a glance

- ✓ **Out of over 220 technological needs, 77 individual solutions could be identified, with only 2 technological gaps relating to milking**
- ✓ **Not all solutions are yet available or affordable to small ruminant farmers**
- ✓ **More research on technology development for small ruminant farmers' needs is needed**
- ✓ **More training and advice on how to use the existing technologies is needed.**

What is the challenge?

- There is not much research on the adaptation of technologies for small ruminant systems
- Research on innovative technologies tend to have focused on larger species in intensive settings
- Sheep and goats are often perceived as having a lower individual value than other larger species
- This leads on to a perceived lack of value of technologies for sheep and goats

What did we learn from Sm@RT?

In the project, the following steps were taken to identify the gaps between farmers' technological needs and existing technologies:

- Out of **over 220 needs**, **77 individual technological solutions** potentially exist for small ruminant farmers
- Although there are **few gaps**, not all solutions are available (prototypes) or affordable to farmers.
- Some of the needs were related to **training and knowledge** (especially for meat sheep and dairy goats) or were **outside farmers' control** (particularly for dairy goats).

What do we recommend?

- ✓ **More investment in research on technology specific to small ruminants, particularly regarding milking**
- ✓ **There are few gaps in knowledge or technologies between farmers' needs and solutions, however, encouraging development to market of prototypes is crucial, as is the affordability of the technology**
- ✓ **Training and pen-side advice is crucial, and need to be further encouraged by policies**

